

CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF COMPLEX DISEASES IN SELF TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Diseases of osteoporosis and the assessment of the patient is taken from the degree of fracture as a marker of many diseases. But bone mineral density (SMZ) is also associated with disease and the risk of fracture. Metabolic disorders associated with secondary osteoporosis are 2-3 times higher in women and in men with hip fractures and vertebral fractures. Globally, osteoporosis is the most common metabolic, bone disease, affecting more than 200 million people worldwide. In Europe, the United States and Japan, 75 million people are diagnosed with osteoporosis. As SMZ decreases, osteoporosis increases with age. Senile osteoporosis is more common in people over 70 years of age. Secondary osteoporosis can occur in any person. Although bone loss in women begins gradually, it accelerates menopause, with delivery at age 50 and beyond. The incidence of postmenopausal osteoporosis is highest in 50-70 women. Women are higher on osteoporosis. Half of postmenopausal women have fractures associated with life and osteoporosis; Ush develops a spinal deformity in 25% of women, and 15% experience hip fractures. Hip fractures are similar in different ethnicities.

Osteoporosis is a disease of the bones characterized by the fragility of the defendant. This is entirely due to a lack of calcium in the body, a disease caused by a deficiency in the skeletal system. People with osteoporosis are at risk of life-threatening injuries, as simple injuries or collisions can lead to bone fractures, such as knocking on the door, table, desk, or other equipment. When it is healthy, it can be dangerous for people with osteoporosis.

Causes of osteoporosis

According to statistics, osteoporosis is more common in women, especially if there are hormonal imbalances or menopause in the future. Smoking, drinking, eating habits, keeping the factors that contribute to the disease. In older people, the risk of developing osteoporosis is explained by a large or weakened tendency. This is due to the treatment of osteoporosis, especially hormonal disorders. Hormonal changes are typical for climatic women, such as age, menstruation, temperature,

artificial insemination. So, the causes of osteoporosis are:

Mongoloid / Europoid people are more likely to get sick. Statistically, people of African American descent have never been diagnosed with osteoporosis (rarely, if ever, in the medical field);

- Bone thinness - it can be congenital or acquired;
- People over the age of 65 - from this age the body begins to lose calcium, which is difficult to replace;
- Hereditary (genetic) factor - Osteoporosis can also be caused by a genetic factor, but not always. The degree of closeness of relatives does not play a role;
- Feminine - Osteoporosis occurs in 87% of cases in women against the background of hormonal changes throughout their lives.

In addition to the causes of the disease, there are risk factors that lead to it:

- Deficiencies by the digestive system;
- Pancreatic dysfunction;
- Changes in the ovaries, their removal;
- Female climax;
- Deficiency of vitamin D and calcium in the diet;
- Long-term use of hormonal drugs;
- Regular consumption of alcohol;
- Regular smoking;
- Long-term use of corticosteroids and antiepileptic drugs;
- Any disorders of the endocrine glands;

- Adrenal insufficiency.

Types of osteoporosis

In medicine, there are three different types of osteoporosis, all of which have specific causes in their origin:

Aging osteoporosis - occurs against the background of calcium deficiency, slows down the renewal of bone cells. This type of osteoporosis is more common in older people, especially those over 70 years of age. In women, it develops after menopause.

Secondary osteoporosis - this type of osteoporosis occurs in only 5% of cases. This is due to the fact that any other disease can adversely affect the skeletal system or long-term use of certain types of drugs.

Idiopathic osteoporosis - This type of osteoporosis is also called youth osteoporosis. Because the disease occurs in young children, even newborns. The cause of this disease is still unknown.

Stages of development of osteoporosis

Doctors distinguish three stages in the development of osteoporosis, based on which the severity of the disease is determined.

First degree. Doctors detect a decrease in bone density, a decrease in bone shadow. Usually, the first degree of osteoporosis is detected as a result of prophylactic examinations because it is asymptomatic.

Intermediate. By this period, a significant decrease in bone density, deformations in the vertebrae are detected. The peculiarity of this level is that the person feels pain in the bones, joints and muscles.

Obvious osteoporosis. X-rays show a clear blurring of the bones. By this time, osteoporosis can be easily diagnosed without further examination.

Symptoms of osteoporosis

The danger of the disease is that it goes away without symptoms in the early stages. Therefore, a person does not feel that osteoporosis is developing. The following symptoms of osteoporosis should be considered:

Hemorrhoids in the lower parts of the body at night - this is not due to stress, fatigue and uncomfortable sleep;

- Low back pain - not constant, occurs from time to time, the intensity of pain varies;
- Deficiencies in the digestive system - this is observed in severe deformation of the vertebrae, the bones "press" on the internal organs;
- Constant tiredness - this is a metabolic disorder in which the body has difficulty concentrating;
- Diabetes mellitus - in this case it is necessary to consult a doctor immediately to quickly determine the cause of osteoporosis;
- Defects in the oral cavity - multiple spots, plaque on the teeth, frequent stomatitis and periodontitis;
- The onset of allergic reactions, increased reactions in people who have not previously been allergic to these products;
- Fractures of the nails on the hands and feet, their displacement;

In addition, people with osteoporosis are less likely to have gray hair and increased heart rate. There are a number of signs that can never be denied, they are:

Persistent pain between the shoulders;

- Spinal curvature;
- Increased fragility of large and small bones;
- General muscle weakness;
- Stunted growth.

The above conditions are irreversible, and medical care can stop the development of the disease in the patient and improve his general condition.

Osteoporosis of the pelvic joint

Doctors treat pelvic osteoporosis as a separate type. But its origin is the same as all osteoporosis. The most dangerous aspect of this type of disease is a fracture of the femur, which is the cause of fractures of the femur in older people. In some cases, the femur is completely paralyzed. Modern medicine treats pelvic osteoporosis in the early and middle stages by endoprosthesis.

Diagnosis of osteoporosis

- X-rays of the bones and spine.
- Densitometry - bone strength is determined using ultrasound, X-ray and computed tomography.

X-ray examination does not allow to diagnose the disease at an early stage. X-rays do not show this, even when the bone mass is reduced by 20-30%. He can only work in the later stages.

Bone densitometry shows the exact amount of bone mass and mineral density. This is also called bone screening.

If the woman is healthy, a densitometry should be performed after the age of 65. Doctors are unanimous on this. However, even if you are young, if your doctor suspects that you have brittle bones, you can have a densitometry earlier. Ask your doctor why he or she prescribed this test for you.

Some preparation is required before landing. This diagnostic apparatus determines the amount of minerals in the bone by means of X-rays. If you live in a remote village, you may have to go to the center. If you are taking calcium, you should stop taking it the day before the diagnosis. Otherwise, the results may be incorrect.

Biochemical analysis of the blood is also performed to diagnose osteoporosis and to determine the amount of various hormones (estrogens, thyroid hormones), vitamin D, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, as well as markers that break down bone tissue and create new ones.

Principles of treatment of osteoporosis

Treatment of osteoporosis is a very complex process. He should be treated by a number of specialists, including an immunologist, rheumatologist, neurologist, endocrinologist, orthopedist-traumatologist. It is important to keep the metabolism in the bones normal. Prevention of bone fractures, reduction of pain, increasing the patient's physical activity are also the main goals of the treatment process.

Osteoporosis is treated with medication. The doctor prescribes medication on an individual basis, for example, if osteoporosis occurs in women during menopause, she is given hormonal therapy. If the disease is age-related, vitamin D and calcium are prescribed.

Almost all patients are prescribed a special diet, therapeutic physical training and massage. Of course, any physical exertion should be kept to a minimum, and only a doctor can prescribe it, taking into account the fragility of the bones. Unfortunately, osteoporosis is not completely cured, proper diet, exercise and treatment prescribed by a doctor can slow the progression of the disease and improve the overall condition of the patient.

Treatment of osteoporosis with folk remedies

Note: In the treatment of osteoporosis, folk remedies are used only as an adjunct. In any case, it is necessary to consult a doctor and take medical treatment!

Mummy

When osteoporosis is diagnosed, it is recommended to take mummy balloons twice a day. Highlights include:

- Mummy balloons should be like the head of a matchstick;
- Dissolve the mummy in 50-70 ml of water;
- This remedy should be taken 20 minutes before meals;
- The treatment period is 20 days.
- Treatment can be done up to 5 times a year, but every 2-3 weeks.

Eggs and lemon

Squeeze 10 lemon juices and mix 6 chicken eggs in it. After that, the mixture should be left for 6 days. On day 7, take the mixture and add 150 ml of cognac and 300 g of honey. Mix well and leave in a dark warm room. It is recommended to take 1 teaspoon after each meal. This procedure is not recommended for gastrointestinal disorders (gastritis, ulcers).

Green cocktails

In osteoporosis, it is better to add "green" cocktails to the diet. What makes them unique:

- Rich in nutrients - 60% of fruits and 40% of vegetables;
- Very easy to absorb - they are prepared by a blender and ready to be absorbed;
- Contraindications to these cocktails (rarely in case of allergy to certain fruits), no side effects at all;
- Every cocktail contains a lot of calcium.

How to make a green cocktail

You will need a powerful blender to make this cocktail. Because the fiber in plants needs to be well digested. It takes 60% fruit and 40% greens to make a classic cocktail. In some cases, it is unpleasant to drink a cocktail of this proportion. Therefore, it is possible to increase the proportion of fruits. For example, 80% fruits and 20% greens. You can choose any fruit for the cocktail. However, softer, faster-absorbing fruit cocktails are more beneficial. For example, like bananas or dates. Apple and pear cocktails are usually sour. It is recommended to drink the

cocktail in the morning on an empty stomach. In general, there is no limit to the number of cocktails per day.

Making a cocktail from calcium-rich products

In osteoporosis, it is better to use calcium-rich products to make a "green" cocktail. For example:

Cabbage is a "champion" of calcium storage. To make a cocktail from barley cabbage, take 5 leaves, mix 4 pears and mint in 500 ml of water. All products are mixed in a blender and drunk throughout the day. If you want a sharper cocktail, use apples instead of pears and citric acid instead of mint.

One glass of turnip cocktail contains 250 mg of calcium. To make a cocktail, take 1-2 turnip leaves, mix 5-6 peaches and 500 ml of water. Take it out of the blender and drink it throughout the day.

Although Chinese cabbage does not contain a lot of calcium, it is very useful in osteoporosis as a "green" cocktail. To do this, take a few cabbage leaves, mix them with 2 mangoes and 500 ml of water, then pass through a blender and drink. Optionally, you can replace the mango with dates or peaches.

Also, don't forget to include sesame seeds, roasted almonds, pistachios, and peanuts. Thus, "green" cocktails are used not only in the treatment of osteoporosis, but also in its prevention.

Diet in osteoporosis

Even if osteoporosis is detected at an early stage and medical treatment is given, the patient should always be on a diet.

Patients with osteoporosis should exclude the following products from the diet:

- Fizzy drinks, caffeinated liquids, such as energy drinks;
- Margarine, mayonnaise and any fatty sauces, preferably replaced with sour cream or olive oil;
- Sheep or beef fat - when eating meat, it is better to separate it from fat;
- Any coffee drinks;
- Alcohol;

Use sugar instead of sugar;

- Sweets.

It is also necessary to reduce protein-rich products - they should not exceed 200 g per day. Given that osteoporosis is caused by metabolic disorders, it is necessary to take less sodium, because if its amount increases, the water-salt balance is disturbed. It is necessary to limit the following products:

- Sausage products, sausages and any smoked meat;
- Fast food;
- Semi-finished products;
- Chips, crackers;
- Salts.

In general, in osteoporosis, the diet is prescribed in different ways. The following are some of the foods that can be eaten in this disease:

- Fish. Any sea and river fish are beneficial to the body in osteoporosis. They should be eaten boiled or steamed, not fried;

• Vegetables. There are no restrictions on the type of vegetables you can eat, even tomatoes, squash, and zucchini;

• Eggs. Eggs are a very useful product for a person with osteoporosis;

• Dairy products. There is no doubt that dairy products are rich in calcium. All you have to do is pay attention to their fat content;

• Greens;

• Fruits, berries;

• All kinds of nuts and pistachios;

• Any type of mushroom;

• Legumes;

• Vegetable oils.

Although there are many unrestricted products for osteoporosis, consult your doctor to take them in moderation. The diet for osteoporosis is as follows:

• Eat at least 5 meals a day;

• The interval between meals should not exceed 3.5 hours;

• It is not necessary to follow a monodiet, for example, to consume only one product per day;

• It is better to eat home-cooked food;

• It is better to eat yogurt or fruit on the street on an empty stomach;

• It is recommended to eat meat with vegetables.

Diet alone is not the answer to the disease, it is the only cure. Osteoporosis is a serious and difficult process to treat. But that doesn't mean you have to lie down to

protect your bones from depression. Instead, it is necessary to try to overcome the disease using active exercise, drug treatment, diet, folk remedies. The more you try, the happier you will be.

Prevention of osteoporosis

To prevent osteoporosis in old age, you need to eat right and lead a healthy lifestyle from a young age. Calcium-rich foods such as skim milk, yogurt, cauliflower, fish, cheese, alcohol and tobacco, and physical activity are recommended. A person under the age of 65 should consume 1000 mg of calcium per day, and after 65 - 1500 mg of calcium.

When the usual preventive measures do not work, doctors resort to medication. But remember, they are not to be taken for granted. Because any drug has side effects. Calcium alone does not cure osteoporosis. Because it is very difficult for the body to absorb. Calcium and vitamin D should be balanced. Only a doctor can do that.

During menopause, women are prescribed the hormone estrogen to prevent osteoporosis. It is also recommended to pay special attention to physical education. After the age of 40, all women should have their thyroid checked and, if necessary, treated.

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